

UniChem: The state-of-the art molecular chemistry
supercomputing environment

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Earlier this year CSIRO, as the first and so far the only site in Australia, installed the *UniChem*TM package from Cray Research on its Cray Y-MP machine. *UniChem* is an easy-to-use supercomputing environment for computational chemistry. The primary uses of *UniChem*'s are in chemical, pharmaceutical, petrochemical and chemical physics research as well as in automotive, electronics or aerospace industries. *UniChem* is a distributed environment: a graphical user interface resides on a Silicon Graphics workstation and the computational part on Cray supercomputers. The computational part of *UniChem* consists of three high-performance, state of the art programs, each designed for the specific type of calculations.

MNDO90, a semi-empirical program applicable to molecules containing up to approximately 500 atoms, developed at the University of Wuppertal, Germany

DGauss, an ab initio density functional program applicable to molecules and clusters containing up to approximately 200 atoms, developed at Cray Research. DGauss is well suited for metals, transition metals and inorganic systems

CADPAC, an ab initio Hartree-Fock program developed at the University of Cambridge, applicable to systems containing up to 50 atoms.

*UniChem*TM software environment from Cray Research, Inc. is a new product; the current version 1.1 was introduced on the market only a couple of months ago. CSIRO is the only institution in Australia that has the *UniChem* license. We will describe the *UniChem* in some detail and present the CSIRO experience with the software.

I. INTRODUCTION

“Every attempt to employ mathematical methods, in the study of chemical questions, must be considered profoundly irrational and contrary to the spirit of chemistry. If mathematical analysis should ever hold a prominent place in chemistry - an aberration which is happily almost impossible - it would occasion a rapid and widespread degeneration of that science.”

Auguste Comte, (1798-1857), in *Philosophie positif* [1]

Čársky and Urban wrote in the preface to their book [2] that as late as in 1960 almost all of ab initio experience was derived from diatomic LCAO calculations and out of approximately eighty calculations, three-fourths were for diatomic molecules. There were only approximately twenty ab initio calculations for molecules with more than two atoms. Confidence in the quality of calculations for many-center two-electron integrals was much lower for polyatomic than for diatomic molecules. The largest molecule treated was SiH_4 . During the last three decades the computational capability of quantum chemistry has grown in an unprecedented manner. This progress was possible due to the number of important achievements in theoretical quantum chemistry [3], algorithm development, software engineering and obviously in hardware architecture and proliferation of ever more powerful supercomputers [4-7].

Even today the number of atoms that can be treated with the SCF Hartree-Fock

method is of the order of 50. The other *ab initio* computational program, DGauss, that is a part of *UniChem*, is based on the Density Functional Method. When used for a molecular system with 1000 basis functions it requires approximately 350 million integrals to be calculated and they must be processed 20 to 30 times during the self-consistent scheme [5]. DGauss can calculate molecules consisting of up to approximately 200 atoms.

The task of computing the molecular geometry and related molecular properties is one of the Grand Challenge problems in computational science [8]. In the *ab initio* methods such as Self-Consistent Field (SCF) Hartree-Fock [6, 9] the computational effort is dominated by the calculation of overlap integrals and scales like N^4 ; if however the correlation effects are to be included the algorithm scales like N^5 . There are a number of schemes to address the problem of computational bottlenecks [7, 5]. For example, careful parallelization of the quantum chemistry codes using the Autotasking and special compiler options of Cray cf77 compiler, as well as calls to Cray Research mathematical library helped to speed up the Density Functional codes by 7.1 times on the 8 processor Cray Y-MP [5].

A brief and lucid history of the computational quantum chemistry can be found in Ref. [3]. For the general reference on computational quantum chemistry the reader is referred to the standard texts [10, 2, 11].

II. APPLICATIONS OF *UNICHEM*

UniChem is one of the most sophisticated, advanced and user-friendly computational molecular quantum chemistry software products available today. As such it will be useful in all fields of chemical research, both pure and applied. The development consortium, apart from Cray Research, included industrial partners: Du Pont, Monsanto and its subsidiaries G.D. Searle and NutraSweet, Eli Lilly, Exxon and 3M. The application areas could easily be deduced from this list of sponsors. Explicitly the key application areas of *UniChem* include drug design, agrochemicals, polymers, catalysis, speciality chemicals, environmental studies, advanced structural, optical, electronic and magnetic materials and many others.

Supercomputational science entered the domain of medicine and biology [1, 6] where the studies such as interactive molecular modelling, drug design/drug interactions (cancer chemotherapy, orphan drugs) [12-14], binding studies (binding site properties), structure/function relationships as applied to drug effectiveness and cell receptor structures can all be substantially boosted by the application of *UniChem* software or software tools such as Gaussian90 [6].

In engineering and chemical engineering *UniChem* can be integrated into large scale problems embodying the molecular structure, properties, synthesis, efficient production cycle, and even the environmental implications of the industrial synthesis process [15].

III. *UNICHEM*, THE SOFTWARE

The *UniChem* consists of five programs. They are: 1) the graphical user interface residing on the local Silicon Graphics workstation, 2) the communication program RCagent, allowing a client (workstation) to communicate with a server (a Cray Research supercomputer) and 3)-5) the three integrated computational chemistry

programs (MNDO91, DGauss and CADPAC 4.0). The User Guide [16] describes the programs in detail. The chemistry codes description can be found in Ref. [17].

A. User interface

Visualization of the computed results, animation of the time-dependent processes and the high quality graphics is essential for the computational chemist [3, 18]. *UniChem* satisfies the need of such high quality graphical representation of the input molecules and the calculated results and properties. *UniChem* has a distributed architecture. The scientist working on the Silicon Graphics workstation control the program on one side of *UniChem* window, and through it he can

- build molecular structures, either with single atoms or through a molecular fragment library
- edit structures
- set up the input to the calculation through a graphical point-and-click display
- launch the calculation on the Cray supercomputer through simple menus
- monitor the progress of the calculation
- graphically analyse the computed data from the calculation

The *UniChem*TM contains three standard libraries of chemical fragments: amino acids, hydrocarbons and organic fragments. The user can build a molecule from either constituent atoms or library fragments, save his own structures, and build his own libraries of fragments and molecules. Figure 1 depicts the main screen of *UniChem* in the build mode, with the menu options on the top, a canvas with the C_{60} molecule and the periodic table, coordination table and some other selection buttons on the right part of the screen.

FIG. 1. The main screen of *UniChem* in the build mode, with the menu options on the top, a canvas with the C_{60} molecule and the periodic table, coordination table and some other selection buttons on the right part of the screen.

B. Distributed environment - RAgent

UniChem is a good example of network supercomputing. The researcher uses a local workstation to build molecules and launch the calculations on the remote Cray systems. The local workstation and the Cray supercomputer communicate using the standard network protocols TCP/IP and a daemon running on the Cray supercomputer called RAgent.

C. Computational chemistry programs

The computational part of *UniChem* consists of three high-performance, state of the art programs, each designed for specific type of calculations [17].

1. MNDO91

The MNDO91 is a semi-empirical program developed over the last twenty or so years by Walter Thiel and co-workers in the University of Wuppertal in Germany [19]. The acronym stands for the modified neglect of differential overlap, a method in which some of the diatomic two-center electron-electron integrals representing the repulsion are set to zero (neglected). The Hamiltonian is balanced by introducing the experimental data for the energy expression, usually derived from the x-ray diffraction on molecules of similar geometry and composition.

The MNDO91 is dominated by matrix operations; the algorithm scales like N^3 . The method is very efficient and fast. Recently a 540-atom carbon cluster was calculated using MNDO90, achieving the speed of 2.2 GFLOPS on Cray Y-MP supercomputer [4].

A researcher can select a model Hamiltonian: MNDO, AM1, PM3, or older methods like MNDO/H, MNDOC, MINDO3 and CNDO/2.

The calculations, depending on the choice of input parameters may include:

geometry optimization, energy, gradient and transition state search, force constants. One can select molecular orbitals (either HOMO, LUMO or up to 10 highest occupied and 5 lowest unoccupied). Thermodynamic properties such as heat capacity, free energy, entropy and enthalpy can be calculated at ten standard temperatures (273.15, 298.15, 300 and every 100 centigrade up to 1000K) or at 25 temperatures, where the user has to specify the minimum, temperature increase, and the number of intervals to be included in the calculations.

2. *DGauss*

DGauss is an ab initio density functional program applicable to molecules and clusters containing up to approximately 200 atoms, including elements from hydrogen to xenon, developed by Jan W. Andzelm at Cray Research. DGauss, unlike the Hartree-Fock method, takes into account the electron correlations, hence it is particularly well suited for metals, transition metals and inorganic systems [20].

A researcher has a choice of global orbital and auxiliary basis sets (DZVP, DZVP2, TZVP, Pople, and A1, A2, A3, P1 respectively). The calculations may include the non-local correction after the final self consistent step (Becke-Perdew or Becke-Stoll-Preuss-Pavlidou).

The calculated properties include the optimized geometry, molecular orbitals (either HOMO, LUMO or up to 10 highest occupied and 5 lowest unoccupied), total electron density, spin density and electrostatic potential.

3. *CADPAC*

CADPAC is an ab initio Hartree-Fock program developed by R. Amos and co-workers at the University of Cambridge, England, applicable to systems containing up to 50 atoms. CADPAC module is comparable in methodology and functionality

to Gaussian90. It appears that CADPAC has larger number of different basis of functions and the user interface makes it much easier to use than Gaussian90 [9].

The Hartree-Fock basis sets include some twenty different choices, depending on the type of atom and the orbital. A user can also define his own basis sets. Some of the molecular properties obtained for the Hartree-Fock CADPAC program at final, optimized geometry are: static polarizability and hyperpolarizability, magnetic susceptibility and dynamic polarizability and hyperpolarizability.

IV. CSIRO EXPERIENCE AND CONCLUSIONS

At the time of writing the researchers from the following CSIRO Divisions have used *UniChem* in their work: Division of Coal and Energy in Sydney, Division of Biomolecular Engineering, Division of Chemicals and Polymers, and Division of Information Technology, all in Melbourne.

Following are opinions about *UniChem* from CSIRO users.

"The Fourier Transform Infrared Emission Spectroscopy (FTIRES) project has to date centred on developing the experimental side of high temperature vibrational analysis of materials. Our interest in Unichem is mainly in the normal coordinate analysis facility which both DGauss and CADPAC provide, and which will allow us to extend the theoretical interpretation of experimental data. In addition, we are in the process of applying FTIRES to surface studies of catalytic materials, and hope to use DGauss to model the absorption of molecules to the surfaces. It appears to us, that the facility to use Unichem would be of significant benefit to our project. The package is particularly suited for users who are unfamiliar with the theoretical methods involved, and indeed is unique in providing access to high level calculations via a graphical interface. This aspect, as well as the expected accuracy of these high level programs, would attract users from a wide range of research areas."

The number of other researchers from the same group expressed interest in *UniChem*.

"I think Unichem is a good interface to the MO packages. It does have a number of limitations (some of these may be corrected in the current version) but appears better than some others I have used. It is probably worth the money simply to get access to CADPAC and DGAUSS."

Some of the limitations in the current version of *UniChem* noted by CSIRO users were: it is not possible to edit text input, there is no integrated molecular mechanics package, it is not possible to do path calculations and to compare structures.

I have installed and tested *UniChem* on seven Silicon Graphics workstations in the first month of our license. It takes less than 30 minutes to install *UniChem* remotely on the Silicon Graphics workstation, provided it is configured in a standard way. I also ran a number of quantum chemical calculations for the carbon C_{60} molecule and the quaternary ammonium salt, DDAB consisting of 84 atoms. The results for the C_{60} total electron density obtained from MNDO91 were later used to identify the collective plasmon modes on the molecule [21]. Figures 2 and 3 represent some examples of calculations using MNDO91 program. I find using *UniChem* is very easy. A practising computational chemist would be able to learn how to use *UniChem*, launch the job on a Cray supercomputer and analyze the data in a matter of an hour.

The user interface is user friendly and appealing, in fact it is one of the best I have known in *real scientific* applications. The DGauss program is an important asset of the package. The density functional method, although widely used in solid state and surface physics [22-27], is only beginning to compete with more established chemistry schemes like self-consistent Hartree-Fock calculations. It is superior for studies of metallic and especially transition metal compounds. The promise of in-

terfacing Gaussian92 and possible utilization of MOPAC, as well as improvement in the efficiency of the programs, colour printing formats and many other features make *UniChem* an ideal, comprehensive tool for computational studies of molecules, their geometry and various properties.

FIG. 2. 2D cross-section along the plane parallel to the pentagonal face of the C_{60} molecule showing the total density of valence electrons.

FIG. 3. 3D representation of the surfaces of constant total electron density on the C_{60} molecule. The density was calculated using MNDO method

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